

Original article

Exploration of drug-drug interactions in prescriptions of Libyan practitioners in community pharmacies

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Abstract: The drug-drug interactions (DDIs) are actions or events that occur when two or more drugs administered together, may cause a clinical significance or not. There are certain factors that may affect the severity of DDIs such as age, gender, number of drugs prescribed, and physician specialists. This study aims to answer: Is there DDI in Libyan community pharmacies? In addition, to explore the factors that might be affecting DDI. Drug Interactions Checkers are used. 200 prescriptions were collected randomly from two different areas (high and low income), 100 from each one and were used to investigate the DDIs by using two different sources (Drugs.com and BNF platforms), bearing in mind, age, gender, prescribers' specialty, and drug number (prescription size). A personal interview questionnaire with pharmacists for investigate a source of DDI knowledge was considered. The correlation test was used to analysis the findings. The randomly selected sample has 316 drug combinations. The study has revealed a minimum of three drugs (46.0%). In general, Drugs.com was the richer source of DDI than BNF (66.5% and 34.5%, respectively). It is found that 66.5% (67.0% of this is moderate DDI) of these combinations have DDI by Drugs.com. A significant correlation between DDI and gender (male > female, $p = 0.035$) was found. In a state of residential areas, the results are similar in both selected pharmacies. Most moderate DDIs (21.0% and 15.0%) are prescribed by orthopedics and psychiatrists, respectively. The observational interview questionnaire indicated that 100% of the participating pharmacists had no source of knowledge regarding DDI, 100% of 200 prescriptions had no chick it regarding DDI and 100% of found DDI is released to use by community pharmacies to patients. More than half of the prescribed drug combinations have DDIs (classified as moderate DDIs), and all of them are released for use by pharmacists.

Introduction

All used drugs have the potential for produce benefits and risks, that particular drug response is affected by its concentration and sometimes its metabolites, at the site of action [1]. This subject is studied under pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamics phases. Patients have differences in their response to the same drug, this is related to age,

gender, disease, genetic, and the presence of other drugs. Patients have to receive several drugs at the same time, this is because of combination therapy. In addition, the patient may suffer from several conditions, and each one should be treated with one or more drugs. As a result, the potential interactions of these drugs will occur within the body which

could be have no clinical significance, severe interactions due to toxicity, or ineffective therapy by antagonism [1]. Drug-drug interaction (DDI) is a co-administration of two or more drugs. It could decrease or increase the action of some drugs, or cause adverse effects and unintended consequences [2]. During the early 1960s, study showed there are many drugs that enhance or inhibit the metabolism of another drug [3]. In 1965, the first international symposium on drug interactions and their clinical importance was conducted. Accordingly, the DDIs issue became the subject of several symposia and reviews in medical journals. The Swedish Drug Regulatory Agency required the pharmaceutical industry to annual reviews of DDI in the national formulary. Besides that, there was an increasing number of reports concerning DDIs and their metabolic interactions. That leads to increasing development and understanding of sophisticated *in vitro* systems for the investigation of drug biotransformation processes. Many reports of DDIs based on *in vitro* findings of patient-lacked clinical relevance added confusion and some doubt rather than systematic knowledge [3]. Cascorbi [4] suggested problems can be limited by use of Electronic Prescribing Systems (EPS), which can alert the user early on the possible interactions and can assist in drug selection and dosage form. DDIs lead to desired or/and undesired effects, which can in turn either potentiate or weaken each other [5]. The source of DDI knowledge: Drug-interaction alerting is one of several types of computerized medication-related clinical decision-support (CDS) used to improve patient safety [5] such as different computer platforms such as Drug Interaction Checker (DIC) [6]. In addition, the Personal Digital Assistant (PDA) is frequently used for finding DDIs, and it often derives from familiar textbooks, handbooks, and internet sources that can be updated regularly. It can also be accessible at the point of patient care, because it is easy to use, and is expected to substitute for standard references [7], for example, community pharmacists in Finland are obliged to ensure the safe and appropriate use of prescriptions, and identifying possible DDIs by developed electronic medication risk management databases and tools, such as EBMEDS [8]. The

Drug Interaction Checkers were drugs.com database which is an American online website that has many choices about the drugs to assist Health care providers. DDIs classification is derived into four classes, major, moderate, minor and unknown [9]. British National Formulary (BNF), is a printed edition updated twice a year, and there is an online platform updated monthly, trusted by healthcare professionals in the UK and all over the world. The DDIs are classified into four classes, i.e. severe, moderate, mild and unknown [10]. DDIs are one of the most significant problems with prescribed drugs [11]. Several studies pointed out that a prescriber's ability is limited to recognize well-documented DDIs. The prescriber rely on pharmacist as a key source of DDI information. However, studies indicate that the ability of the pharmacist to identify important drug interactions is also lacking [5]. The high hazard of unwanted DDIs even occurs in developed countries. 20.0% of the adverse drug events responsible for 770 000 deaths are due to DI in the USA. In Sudan, primary health services are not available to the majority of the patients, therefore, the impact of DI will be higher. 95.0% of the dispensers in community pharmacies provided a DI. As a result, it is suggested to ensure the appropriateness of the prescribed medicines [12]. The result of a sub-therapeutic dose can increase the concentration of the drug, therefore, the risk of side effects could be higher [13]. FDA defines the possible result of DI as death, life-threatening, hospitalization (initial or prolonged), disability, permanent change, injury, damage or disruption in the patient's body function/structure, physical activity, or quality of life. Congenital anomaly, and requires intervention to prevent permanent impairment or damage [14]. Increasing the risks of DDIs with poly-pharmacy [14]. With age, increase in multi-morbidity which necessitates several drugs for one patient at the same time, for the example the average 65-years-old patient has five drugs simultaneously, and this could be increase in between 75-84 years-old patients. According to a European study, patients with a mean age of 81 years 34.0% to 68.0% were taking more than five drugs [4], therefore, the possibility of DDIs occurrence will be high [15].

According to the WHO, ADR database contains more than 3.8 million suspected adverse drug reaction reports from 82 countries due to the DDIs [13], accounting for 5.0% to 26.0% of all adverse drug reactions [15]. DDIs are responsible for up to 02.0% to 03.0% of hospital admissions [11]. The relationship of age with DDIs, number of drugs with DDIs, and prescribers and DDIs, have been reported [4, 15, 16]. Indeed, cardiologists and dermatologists of physician specialists have direct and indirect relationships, respectively, with DDIs [16]. Males and females have direct and indirect relationships with DDIs [17]. Medication-taking behavior may be affected by traditional consumer choices under a budget constraint in that increased prices lead to decreased utilization. There is a relationship between economic area (high and low income) and DDIs [18]. Thus, this study aims to estimate the prevalence of major, moderate and minor DDIs in Libyan community pharmacies, and to evaluate the association of these interactions with patient characteristics.

Materials and methods

This study was approved by Ethical Committee of Scientific Research (ECSR, 0124-2023). It is about investigating DDIs in prescriptions of Libyan practitioners from two community pharmacies, and included the analysis of patient characteristics and prescription size (number of drugs). Descriptive and correlation analysis of DDIs and patient characteristics such as age, gender, source of prescriptions, medical specialties, and prescription size (number of drugs). An interview questionnaire about using databases or platforms to indicate the DDIs at pharmacies. The dispensing behavior of pharmacists to dispense prescribed prescriptions was measured. Over the last June, July, and August 2023, 200 prescriptions were collected from two different pharmacies in different areas of Tripoli city, namely, Khalifa pharmacy (low income) and Almenshia pharmacy (high income). Thus, 100 prescriptions for each one, and the prescriptions contained at least three drugs. The analysis of DDIs was performed by using the Drug Interactions Checkers from different committees database

(USA) [9]. BNF was printed edition that examined the DDIs from Appendix 1-Interactions (UK) [10]. The interview questionnaire included: is there a program desktop used at these two pharmacies as a DDIs checker? No, there are not specific strategies to explore DDIs of prescriptions. Most pharmacists deal alone with different sources such as BNF, reading the medication's leaflets, or just depending on their knowledge. Does the pharmacist who dispensed the drugs of prescriptions have DDI? Yes, he dispensed all prescriptions. Data was calculated as frequency and percentage. A Person's correlation coefficient was also used.

Results

In this study, using Pearson correlation coefficient, there is a negative significant of correlation between gender and the number of drugs ($r = -0.149$, $p = 0.035$). This means that the female has significantly less number of drugs than the male. Alternatively, there is no significant of correlation between age and number of drugs ($r = 0.072$, $p = 0.312$). The number of drugs may correlate with age increase. There is no correlation at all between physician specialists and the number of drugs ($r = 0.002$, $p = 0.983$), that means, there is no great difference between physician specialists and the number of drugs prescribed. There is no significant of correlation between the source of prescriptions and the number of drugs ($r = 0.095$, $p = 0.179$), which means there is a relationships between the pharmacies where collected data and the number of drugs. This study investigated 316 DDIs and prepared a list of classified DDIs upon to BNF and Drugs.com. These DDIs derived into 164 DDIs (52.0%) in a high residential area (Almenshia pharmacy) and 152 DDIs (48.0%) in a low residential area (Khalifa pharmacy). In **Table 1**, about the Drugs.com database [9], there is 33.5% of investigated DDIs are free from known DDIs. As a result, most of these known DDIs are classified as moderate (44.3%). However, BNF [10] pointed out that 34.4% of investigated DDIs have known DDIs, and most of them are moderate (19.6%) as shown in **Table 2**.

Table 1: Classifications of the studied DDIs according to Drugs.com [9]

Classification of DDIs	Total number	Percentage
Major	36	11.4
Minor	34	10.8
Moderate	140	44.3
Unknown	106	33.5
Total	316	100

Unknown: means there is no interactions

Table 2: Classification of the studied DDIs according to the BNF [10]

Classification of DDIs	Total number	Percentage
Unknown	207	65.5
Mild	15	4.7
Moderate	62	19.6
Severe	32	10.1
Total	316	100

Unknown: means there is insufficient evidence to hazard

As it is shown in **Figure 1**, most interactions are moderate (44.3%). But nearly, an equal percentage between moderate and unknown in the low residential area (18.0% - 19.3%, respectively), but it is clear that moderate DDIs more than other

Figure 1: Distribution of different DDI classes upon residential areas

classes in the high residential area (25.3%). In **Figure 2**, about gender, most of the participants existed in moderate DDI class, where there were more than female participants. In **Table 3**, most of the participants at age of more than 45 years old. The total result is affected by another age group, where the highest percentage in old adults above 45 is for minors then the moderate DDI classes (73.5% - 62.1%, respectively). In **Table 4**, with physician specialist, the highest DDI class is found in the moderate DDI class (n = 140). The scattered number of DI by different physician specialists. The highest number is found in orthopedic physicians then psychiatrists at the moderate DDI class (21% and 15%, respectively).

In **Table 5**, about poly-therapy (prescription size, drug number), 46.2% of the study's samples referred to prescriptions have three drugs with the moderate DDI class (n = 45) and major DDI class (n = 18). In addition, 34.5% of the prescriptions belong to prescriptions that have four drugs with moderate DDI class (n = 51) and major DDI class (n = 11). Then small fractions of DDIs as 07.28%, 05.3%, 04.7%, 0.95% and 0.95% came from prescriptions have a number of drugs of 8, 6, 5, 9 and 7, respectively).

Figure 2: Distribution of different gender on different classes of DDIs

Table 3: Distribution of participants according to their ages in different DDI class

Classification according to Drugs.om	Infants (< 2 years) (%)	Children (2-16 years) (%)	Young adults (> 16-30 years) (%)	Middle-aged (31-45 years) (%)	Old adults > 45 years (%)	Total DDIs (316) (%)
Major	0	0	5.4	32.4	62.2	11.7
Moderate	0	3.6	13.6	20.7	62.1	44.3
Minor	0	2.9	5.9	17.6	73.5	10.8
Unknown	5.7	11.3	13.2	30.1	39.6	33.5
Total of DDIs (316) (%)	1.9	5.7	11.7	25	56.0	100

Table 4: Physician specialists defined by DDI classification

Physician specialty	Major	Minor	Moderate	Unknown	Total
Blood vessels physician	2	0	1	1	4
Cardiologist	4	4	19	5	32
Dentist	1	0	2	2	5
Dermatologist	0	0	0	4	4
Emergency physician	0	0	1	1	2
Fertility specialist	0	0	0	1	1
General Physician	1	3	8	13	25
Gynecologist	0	1	8	11	20
Internist	0	7	14	14	37
Internist, Orthopedist and Rheumatologist	2	0	0	0	2
Neurologist	1	1	9	0	11
Nutritionist	0	0	0	2	2
Oncologist	2	2	11	4	19
Ophthalmologist	0	0	1	2	3
Orthopedic physician	8	3	29	16	56
Otolaryngologist	0	5	3	12	20
Pediatrician	0	1	0	13	14
Plastic surgeon	0	0	0	1	1
Psychiatrist	13	0	21	0	34
Pulmonologist	1	6	4	2	13
Surgeon	1	0	6	0	7
Urologist	0	1	2	1	4
Total	36	34	140	106	316

Table 5: The classification of DDIs according to the number of drugs of prescriptions

Number of drugs	Major	Minor	Moderate	Unknown	Total	Percentage of interactions
3	18	16	45	67	146	46.2
4	11	12	51	35	109	34.49
5	2	2	10	1	15	4.7
6	1	2	12	2	17	5.37
7	0	0	3	0	3	0.95
8	4	2	16	1	23	7.28
9	0	0	3	0	3	0.95
Total	36	34	140	106	316	100

Discussion

In this study, there is a difference between the sources of information and data by the sources, where 200 prescriptions were dispensed with 316 DDIs representing 34.4% and 66.0% in BNF and Drugs.com, respectively. Additionally, there are differences of information between the sources, because online Drugs.com may be more advanced and more flexible than BNF printed form, that is why, they investigated the DDIs of variables by Drugs.com source. Most of the DDIs at the moderate class (44.3%) according to Drugs.com, but in BNF, most of the known DDIs at the moderate class (19.6%). Thus, it is important to make people aware to avoid any risk and severity of the DDI. According to residential areas, it is collected these prescriptions from two different areas agreeing to the economics of the patients (patient adherence), where Almenshia pharmacy (high income area) has 51.9% DDIs, and most of them at the moderate class (25.3%). While, Khalifa pharmacy (low income area) has 48.1%, most of them at the moderate class (19.0%), because there is no vast difference with unknown class (19.3%). Depending on the connection, there is a positive correlation between these areas and the number of drugs without significance. These outcomes also explain a small difference between these two areas, and their relationships with patient economics, where, the high income area has more dispensed

drugs number, and the good adherence in picking the medications by the patients than the low income area. Hence, as health care providers, pharmacists have to be aware when dispensing prescriptions, especially in highly economic areas. In a state of gender, there is a difference between gender and the number of drugs, the males have drugs prescribed more than the females leading to a high DDI, the male has 33.6% of known DDIs, and most of them at a the moderate class (24.4%), while the female subject has 32.5% of known DDIs and most of them at the moderate class (19.5%). In the case of correlation data between age and the number of drugs prescribed, there is a positive correlation between them. The old adult patients aged above 45 has 56.0% of all DDIs more than other age groups, since most of the patients were old adult's ages. This can explain the highest percentage of this group, but it does not prevent to seek the solutions for all the age groups to avoid DDIs, especially for old adults, who have more several health problems. There is relation between physician specialists and the number of drugs prescribed, because they mostly prescribe the drugs depending on the patient's needs. However, as we observed, the orthopedic physicians have DDIs more than other specialists with 56 DDIs and most of them at the moderate class, and the second was psychiatrists have 34 DDIs and most of them at

moderate class. According to the number of drugs, most prescriptions have minimum of three drugs, therefore, the highest percentage of DDIs was 46.2% referred to prescriptions that contained three drugs, and most of them at a moderate class with 45 DDIs and major class, then prescriptions which contain four drugs (34.5% DDIs), and most of them at moderate class. Thus, even with a low number of drugs, DDIs can occur. So, the answers of the interview questionnaire, there are no strategies to indicate DDIs of prescriptions before dispensing at the two areas, according to their answers, they mostly depend on their knowledge, some other sources such as BNF, or reading the leaflets of medications before dispensing. Regarding DDI, all the detected drugs, that have DDI, are dispensed. All the prescriptions have been dispensed. If the pharmacists reject the prescriptions that indicate other reasons such as the drugs are not available, or the prescriptions are not legal or clear, hence, rejection of the prescription an account for other

reasons than the existence of DDI. Regarding age, gender, prescriber specialty, and prescription size are randomly selected. However, a larger sample size from different regions of Libya is required to confirm the parameters related to DDIs. This could solve the difference in detected DDIs by using two sources of analysis used in this study.

Conclusion: More than half of the prescribed drug combinations have DDIs (classified as moderate DDIs), and all of them are released for use by the pharmacist. This fact necessitates the following: provision of an accurate DDI checker, it has to be on a desktop for clinical pharmacist/community pharmacist that is to be familiar with such DDI before dispensing prescriptions. The pharmacist has to stop dispensing the prescriptions if contain DDIs, and he/she should communicate continually with the physician, who prescribed the drugs, to alert and attenuate the severity of these risks.

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Author contribution: JRK & SMA designed the study, collected the data and performed data analysis. FNR collected and performed data analysis. JRK interpreted of data & drafted, and revised the manuscript. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript and agreed to be accountable for its contents.

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Ethical issues: Including plagiarism, informed consent, data fabrication or falsification, and double publication or submission have completely been observed by authors.

Data availability statement: The raw data that support the findings of this article are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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References

1. Rowland M (2008) Introducing pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic concepts. In: Rodrigues D (ed.) Drug-drug interactions. 2nd ed., New York: Informa Healthcare USA. eBook ISBN: 9780429131967
2. Rekić D, Reynolds KS, Zhao P, Zhang L, Yoshida K, Sachar M, Miller MP, Huang MP, Huang SM, Zineh I (2017) Clinical drug-drug interaction evaluations to inform drug use and enable drug access. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 106 (9): 2214-2218. doi: 10.1016/j.xphs.2017.04.016
3. Sjöqvist F, Böttiger Y (2010) Historical perspectives: drug interactions - it all began with cheese. *Journal of Internal Medicine*. 268 (6): 512-515. doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2796.2010.02300.x
4. Cascorbi I (2012) Drug interactions-principles, examples and clinical consequences. *Deutsches Arzteblatt international*. 109 (33-34): 546-556. doi.org/10.3238/arztebl.2012.0546
5. Saverno KR, Hines LE, Warholak TL, Grizzle AJ, Babits L, Clark C, Taylor AM, Malone DC (2011) Ability of pharmacy clinical decision-support software to alert users about clinically important drug-drug interactions. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*. 18 (1): 32-37. doi: 10.1136/jamia.2010.007609

6. Lalagkas PN, Poulentzas G, Tsiolis L, Berberoglou E, Litina DH, Douros A, Kontogiorgis C, Constantinides T (2022) Investigating potential drug-drug interactions from Greek e-prescription data. *Current Drug Safety*. 17 (2): 114-120. doi.org/10.2174/1574886316666210816115811
7. Kheshti R, Aalipour M, Namazi S (2016) A comparison of five common drug-drug interaction software programs regarding accuracy and comprehensiveness. *Journal of Research in Pharmacy Practice*. 5 (4): 257-263. doi.org/10.4103/2279-042X.192461
8. Kallio S, Eskola T, Airaksinen M, Pohjanoksa-Mäntylä M (2021) Identifying gaps in community pharmacists' competence in medication risk management in routine dispensing. *Innovations in Pharmacy*. 12 (1): doi: 10.24926/iip.v12i1.3510
9. Drug interactions checker (2023) Drug Interaction Online. Available at: http://www.drugs.com/drug_interactions.php (Accessed: September 2023).
10. Joint Formulary Committee (2022) British National Formulary. London: BMJ and Royal Pharmaceutical Society, UK.
11. Tragni E, Casula M, Pieri V, Favato G, Marcobelli A, Trotta MG, Catapano AL (2013) Prevalence of the prescription of potentially interacting drugs. *PLoS ONE*. 8 (10): e78827. doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0078827
12. Hamadoun R, Albashair ED, Mohammed FM, Yousef BA (2022) The practice of the community pharmacists in managing potential drug-drug interactions: a simulated patient visits. *Integrated Pharmacy Research and Practice*. 11: 71-84. doi: 10.2147/IPRP.S355675
13. Strandell J, Bate A, Lindquist M, Edwards R (2008) Drug-drug interactions - a preventable patient safety issue? *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*. 65 (1): 144-146. doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2125.2007.02981.x
14. Ansari J (2010) Drug interaction and pharmacist. *Journal of Young Pharmacists*. 2 (3): 326-331. doi.org/10.4103/0975-1483.66807
15. Mousavi S, Norouzi M, Ashouri A, Javadi MR, Gholami K, Hadjibabaie M (2014) Study of potential drug-drug interactions in prescriptions of university-based pharmacies. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Care*. 2 (2): 60-65. ID: emr-153306
16. Ahmadizar F, Soleymani F, Abdollahim M (2011) Study of drug-drug interactions in prescriptions of general practitioners and specialists in Iran 2007-2009. *Iranian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 10 (4): 921-931. PMC: 3813067
17. Al Ameri1 MN, Makramalla E, Albur U, Kumar A, Rao P (2014) Prevalence of poly-pharmacy in the elderly: implications of age, gender, co-morbidities and drug interactions. *SOJ Pharmacy & Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 1 (3): 1-7. doi.org/10.15223/2374-6866/1/3/00115
18. Elliott R, Shinogle J, Peele P, Bhosle M, Hughes DA (2008) Understanding medication compliance and persistence from an economics perspective. *Value in Health*. 11 (4): 600-610. doi: 10.1111/j.1524-4733.2007.00304.x
19. Prajapati J, Patel A, Raninga P (2014) Facial age group classification. *IOSR Journal of Electronic and Communication Engineering*. 9 (1): 33-39. doi: 10.9790/2834-09123339